

Silvestro Ganassi and the *Valente* Master (1542–43): Forging a Model of the Perfect Player

Giulia Tettamanti

Introduction

Silvestro Ganassi is widely recognized today for writing the most important book in the history of the recorder and the first treatise about diminutions, *Opera Intitulata Fontegara* (Venice, 1535).¹ He also wrote a two-volume treatise on the viol, *Regola Rubertina* (1542) and *Letitione Seconda* (1543), the latter also containing information on the lute.² But Ganassi was far more than just a player, being known to his peers also as a good painter and a virtuous man with a ‘divine’ intellect. On the title page of *Letitione Seconda*, he promises besides several technical skills to reveal all the secrets that can make one into a *valente* master on the viol and lute. In this article, I explore the philosophical background of this promise, showing what *valente* implied as well as why and how he provides his own overview of the perfect player according to rhetorical ideals.

Ganassi the man

Silvestro Ganassi (1491/92–c.1572) was one of the most influential Venetian instrumentalists of his time.³ At the end of the fifteenth century, his family came from the province of Bergamo, then part of the *terraferma* territories of the Venetian Republic, and settled in the *contrada* (parish) of San Silvestro in Venice, one of the principal areas where the many Bergamasque immigrants were concentrated, and itself part of the greater Rialto area, the city’s main commercial and financial centre. Close to the church and facing the Grand Canal stood the Republic’s main grain distribution warehouse, the Fontego della Farina, a building that also contained what today would be called a shopping arcade as well as flats for the merchants to live in.⁴ Silvestro’s father, Antonio Ganassi, had a barbershop at the sign of *Le tre teste* (The

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¹For a comprehensive summary and assessment of *Fontegara*, see David Lasocki and Robert Ehrlich, *The Recorder* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2022), 60–73.

²Ian Woodfield, *The Early History of the Viol* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1984), chapters 8 and 9, presents a long summary of Ganassi’s technical information on the viol, concluding that ‘The message from Ganassi’s tutor is clear: a proficient technique by itself was not enough for mid-16th-century audiences. Expressive and varied playing was all-important, and technical facility was of use only in so far as it contributed to this end,’ (p.169). He does not address the philosophical background explored in the present article.

³The definitive biography of Ganassi is Marco di Pasquale, ‘Silvestro Ganassi: A Documented Biography’, *Recercare*, 31/1–2 (2019), 29–102, from which the information cited here is taken unless otherwise stated.

Three Heads) in this Fontego, and perhaps the whole family lived there.⁵

This is why they used the epithet 'dal Fontego' in their surname, to differentiate themselves from other branches of the family, such as that of Zacaria dal Trombone in Bologna. And from it also stemmed the name of Silvestro Ganassi's celebrated recorder treatise: *Opera intitolata Fontegara*, a work created by the man from the Fontego.

At that time, barbershops did much more than cut men's hair or perform minor surgeries. They were also places where men went to relax, chat, learn the news, gossip, and listen to music, so all barbers knew how to play musical instruments for the enjoyment of their customers. Of the four sons of Antonio, Silvestro and Girolamo became professional musicians working for the Republic and Giovanni was a part-time barber as well as musician. Collectively, they had their own group called *I sonadori del Fontego* (The Fontego Players), who were hired for celebrations of patron saints in churches and visits to the city by illustrious people.

In 1517, when Silvestro was around 25 years old, he was hired for the *contralto* part in the prestigious *piffari del Doge*, the official wind group of the Venetian Republic, made up of six players: three shawms and three trombones. His brother Girolamo had been one of its trombonists since at least 1504. On the *contralto* part, Silvestro would have played not only shawm but also cornetto, and the entire ensemble would have formed a consort of recorders on suitable occasions. At his side, playing the *soprano* part, was one of the most famous cornettists of the century, Giovanni Maria dal Cornetto (who served from 1502).

Ganassi was not only a musician. In 1543, the same year that on the title page of his *Lettonne seconda* he calls himself *desideroso nella pictura* (passionate about painting), the famous writer Pietro Aretino published a *Dialogo ... nel quale si parla del gioco con moralità piacevole*, later known as *Le carte parlanti*, in which he calls Ganassi 'the Musician-Painter and most divine Philosopher'.⁶ The satirical tone in which he speaks of Ganassi points to a close friendship with him, recalled in Lodovico Dolce's *Dialogo della pittura ... intitolato l'Aretino* (1557), when the interlocutor Fabrini refers to Ganassi in relation to Aretino as 'your virtuoso Silvestro, excellent musician and player of the *Doge*, who draws and paints commendably'.⁷ In between these two works, Ganassi is mentioned in Paolo Pinto's *Dialogo di pittura* (1548) as having 'a divine intellect, elevated spirit, all virtue, and is a good painter'.⁸

Ganassi also became an outstanding music teacher, both in training professional wind musicians and in instructing gentlemen to play the viol (and probably also the recorder) – instruments suited to amateurs. We know from the prefaces of *Regola Rubertina* (1542) and *Lettonne Seconda* (1543) that he taught Ruberto Strozzi and Neri Capponi, who were the dedicatees of these works and also his patrons from 1538 to the mid-1540s. Strozzi and Capponi were Florentines, who had been exiled for political reasons after the Medici returned to

⁵From documentation collected by Di Pasquale (docs 2, 13 and 24) it is not clear whether they lived in the Fontego or next to it, separately or together. The Fontego della Farina was in the form of a C and had an internal court which also served as a boundary with other properties. See *Fontego de la Farina*, Venezia Museo website; <veneziamuseo.it/TERRA/San_Polo/Silvestro/sil_font_farina.htm>.

⁶'Il Musico Pittore, e Philosopho divinißimo', f.35^r. For more details, see Giulia da Rocha Tettamanti, 'Silvestro Ganassi and Pietro Aretino's Talking Cards: a New Reference on the *Fontegara's* Author', *Revista* 4'33", 9/19 (December 2020), 116–26.

⁷'vostro virtuoso Silvestro eccellente musico e sonatore del doge, il quale disegna e depinge lodevolmente'. Di Pasquale, 'Silvestro Ganassi', 74, 96.

⁸'un intelletto divino, tutto elevato, tutto virtù, & è un buon pittore'. Di Pasquale, 'Silvestro Ganassi', 74, 91.

power.⁹ Strozzi's father and uncle, Filippo and Lorenzo, had been extremely active figures in the political, literary and musical scene in Florence, being members of the circles involved in the creation of the madrigal – as in, for example, the discussions about ancient Rome in the gardens of the Rucellai family residence, where Niccolò Machiavelli, among others, read his works.¹⁰ The revival of Classical Roman ideas and literature, especially the rhetorical works of Cicero and Quintilian, was the perfect backdrop for the creation of this new musical genre, which started to distance itself from the institutional imitative counterpoint of the church towards a counterpoint that highlights the meaning the text, seeking the expression of its affect and bringing with it an understanding of the musician no longer as a mathematician, but rather as a communicator, an orator.

Filippo and Lorenzo Strozzi wrote several poems that were set to music by the first madrigalists. Ruberto, having grown up in this environment, acquired a great appreciation for music. Neri Capponi, Ruberto's cousin, worked for the Strozzi family bank. He spent the first part of his exile in Lyon, France, which housed a large community of Florentine exiles, among them the composer Francesco de Layolle (1492–1540), who acted as host to the new arrivals. There they had the custom of getting together to sing madrigals, either at the Strozzi residence or in the gardens of Layolle's residence, in clear nostalgia for the old days of meetings in the Rucellai gardens. Having moved on to Venice in 1538, Capponi kept a *ridotto* – a kind of private club typical of that city where a select group of gentlemen, led by a host, met periodically to discuss aspects of art and literature of interest to them, often graced by the presence of the most prominent artists and literati around. Capponi's interests being musical, his meetings were attended by a group of the best singers and instrumentalists in Venice under the direction of the celebrated chapel master of the Basilica of San Marco, Adrian Willaert (c.1490–1562).

Two testimonies to the excellence of this *ridotto* have survived. First, in the dedication letter of Ganassi's *Letzione Seconda*:

To the illustrious Lord Neri Capponi, from his servant Silvestro Ganassi dal Fontego, instrumentalist of [Venice]....

... furthermore, you being a Parnassus, a Helicon, a Refuge of the virtuous, I judge there is no safer place that it [i.e. my work] could live than next to you. Because if it were accepted by your rare judgment and by that of the sacred and divine *collegio* [fellowship, i.e. the members of the *ridotto*] which with the immortal glory of this magnificent city nestles next to you, the chatter of others would never affect its esteem. Since the Prince of that [*collegio*] is the never-praisable-enough Mr. Adriano [Willaert], new Prometheus of celestial Harmony, humiliator of the past, glory of the present and master of the future century, without

⁹See Richard J. Agee, 'Filippo Strozzi and the Early Madrigal', *Journal of the American Musicological Society*, 38 (1985), 227–37; Martha Feldman, *City Culture and the Madrigal at Venice* (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1995); Katelijne Schiltz, 'Mäzenatentum und Selbstdarstellung im Exil. Die Florentiner "fuorusciti" in Venedig (ca.1536–1546)', *Die Musikforschung*, 56 (2003), 46–53; and Anthony M. Cummings, *The Maecenas and the Madrigalist: Patrons, Patronage, and the Origins of the Italian Madrigal* (Philadelphia, PA: American Philosophical Society, 2004).

¹⁰Cummings, *Maecenas*, chapter 1.

a doubt the universe will like what is praised by his divine judgment.¹¹

Second, in the dedication of the tenor part-book of the *Dialogo della musica* (1544) by the Florentine writer Antonfrancesco Doni, from which we obtain a more detailed view. This part-book is dedicated to Annibale, Marquis Malvicino from the city of Piacenza:

The music that is made in Your Lordship's house, of lutes, [keyboard] instruments, *pifferi* [i.e. shawms and trombones], recorders, [and] voices, and that in the house of the honourable Mr. Alessandro Colombo is very dignified. And that of viols of Mr. Guido della Porta, wonderful. But, if Your Lordship listened to the divinity that I tasted with the ear of the intellect here in Venice, you would be astonished. There is a gentle lady, Polissena Pecorina (wife of a citizen of my birthplace), so virtuous and gentle that I cannot find praise high enough to commend her. One night I heard a consort of viols and voices where she played and sang in the company of other excellent spirits. The perfect maestro of such music was Adriano Willaert, with that diligent invention of his, never before used by musicians, so unified, so sweet, so just, so wonderfully accommodated to the words, that I confessed I had never known what harmony was in all my days except that night. The person fervorous about this music, and in love with such divine composition, is a gentleman, a most excellent spirit, also a Florentine, called Mr. Neri Caponi. With whom, through Mr. Francesco Corboli, a regal man, I became friends. And, by his mercy, I took in, saw and heard such divinity. This Mr. Neri spends hundreds of ducats a year on such virtue. And he keeps it close to himself: not even if it were his father would he hand over a single song. So, since I cannot send you that [music], I will give you this, although it pains me not to be able to show my friendship by better means.¹²

¹¹'Allo Illustre Signor Neri Capon, Il suo Servo Silvestro Ganassi dal Fontego. S. D. [V.]... Oltra che essendo voi un Parnaso, un'Elicona, & uno Asillo di virtuosi, in loco niuno piu sicura non giudicai quella poter vivere, che appo voi. Perche se ella sia accettata dal vostro raro giudicio, & da quello sacro & divino collegio che appo voi con gloria immortale di questa alma Citate, si annida, nulla istimera ella i altrui trasparlamenti che essendovi Principe di quello il non mai a bastanza lodato messer Adriano nuovo Prometheo della celeste Armonia scorno del passato, gloria del presente, & maestro del futuro secolo, quello senza dubbio all'universo piacera che dal suo divino giudicio sia lodato.' All translations from Ganassi are my own.

¹²'AL S. ANNIBALE MARCHESE MALVICINO. La Musica, che si fa in casa V. S. di Liuti, di stromenti, di pifferi, di flauti, di voci, et in casa dell'honorato M. Alessandro Colombo è dignissima, et quella de i violoni del S. Guido della Porta mirabile: mà se la S. V. udisse la divinità, ch'io ho gustato con l'orecchia dell'intelligenza qui in Vinegia stupirebbe. Eccì una gentil donna POLISENA Pecorina (consorte d'un cittadino della mia patria) tanto virtuosa, et gentile, che non trovo lode si alte, che la commendino. Io ho udito una sera un concerto di violoni, et di voci, dove ella sonava, et cantava in compagnia di altri spiriti eccellenti: il maestro perfetto della qual musica era Adriano Villaert di quella sua diligente invention non più usata da' musici, si unita, si dolce, si giusta, si mirabilmente acconcie le parole; ch'io confessai non havere saputo, che cosa sia stata armonia nè miei giorni, salvo in quella sera. L'infervorato di questa musica, et l'innamorato di tanta divina compositione è un gentil'huomo, uno spirito eccellentissimo pur Fiorentino, detto M. Neri Caponi: al quale per mezzo di M. Francesco Corboli huomo Reale fui fatto amico: et mercè sua sentì, vidi, et udì tanta divinità. Questo M. Neri dispensa l'anno le centinaia de ducati in tal virtù; et la conserva appresso di sé; nè se fosse suo padre darebbe fuori un canto. Ora poi ch'io non vi posso mandar quella le dono questa. Ben mi duole non poterle mostrar con maggior mezzo, ch'io li sia amico.' *Dialogo della musica di M. Antonfrancesco Doni Fiorentino* (Venice, 1544), tenor part-book. My translation.

This work by Doni emulates a meeting of a musical *ridotto*. The soprano part-book comes with a dialogue among four interlocutors, who, from time to time, stop talking to sing a madrigal by a known composer, the music for which appears next in this part-book as well as in the other three.¹³ (The dialogue appears only in the soprano.) These testimonies are essential background for Ganassi's viol treatises, to understand how select and erudite his readership in Venice was. When we analyse the depth of his complete oeuvre, we realize that his treatises are no mere tutors for teaching the basics of instruments, but true works of art, created to show the magnificence of his mind, his peers and his city, and to celebrate all of them.¹⁴

Ganassi's viol treatises are in truth a single work in two books: *Regola Rubertina* (1542) is a small introduction and preparation for the important and in-depth part that follows. So much so that, at the end of the *Regola*, he already announces the entire contents of *Lettione Seconda* (1543). This is the reason why the latter, called 'Second Lesson', has no opening engraving, only a frontispiece with a long title that takes up the whole page. Perhaps he was testing the waters before publishing the second book or simply divided the work into two parts to please his patrons. The distance of just one year between the two publications is in fact revealing: in his epilogue to *Lettione Seconda* he observes that it takes five or six or more years to write a book,¹⁵ therefore that work was probably already planned and almost written when he published *Regola Rubertina*. The present article considers these books as a whole. Even though only the second shows clearly his intention to create a model for the player, the first presents in its discourse all the elements related to the model's philosophical background.

Valente and perfect

In the title of *Lettione Seconda*, after an extensive list of technical skills the book proposes to teach, there appears a curious promise: to reveal 'very useful secrets that are appropriate to act as a *valente* master of such an instrument or instruments', the plural being added because he also discusses the lute in this work.¹⁶ *Valente* has the same Latin origin as the English 'valiant', meaning brave, courageous or bold. But in Italian brave was not, and is not, the primary meaning. The *Accademia della Crusca* dictionary, the first published one of the Tuscan language (1612), has the following definition for the term: 'someone who is worthy in his profession, courageous, excellent'.¹⁷ The examples that follow the entry describe an excellent

¹³ See <bibliotecamusica.it/cmbm/viewschedatwbca.asp?path=/cmbm/images/ripro/gaspari/_B/B149/>.

¹⁴ See Giulia da Rocha Tettamanti, 'Silvestro Ganassi: *Obra intitulada Fontegara*. Um estudo sistemático do tratado abordando aspectos da técnica da flauta doce e da música instrumental do século XVI' (master's diss., Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Campinas-SP, 2010), 30–57; Tettamanti, 'A Fontegara de Silvestro Ganassi e a Teoria das Proporções na época de Andrea Gritti (1523–1538)', *Atas do IV Encontro de História da Arte – IFCH/Unicamp* (2008), 1163–72; Pedro Sousa Silva, 'Gammaut and *le sette voce di piu*', symposium paper, academia.edu; Di Pasquale, 'Silvestro Ganassi', 69–73; Dina Maria de Oliveira Titan, 'The Origins of Instrumental Diminution in Renaissance Venice: Ganassi's *Fontegara*' (doctoral thesis, Universiteit Utrecht, 2019), 293–98.

¹⁵ '... le opere son fatte non con poca fatica e non basta la fatica diremo del star cinque o sei o di piu anni in concludere ditta opera...'

¹⁶ 'utilissimi secreti a propositi nell'effetto dil valente di tal strumento e strumenti'. *Effetto* has caught out several modern translators who took it for a cognate. In fact, in this context, especially when associated with the verb *fare* (to make), it means action rather than effect. *Fare l'effetto del valente* means to do what he does that makes him excellent, or in other words, to act as.

¹⁷ 'Che vale assai nella sua professione, prode, eccellente.' *Vocabolario degli accademici della Crusca*; <lessicografia.it/ricerca_libera.jsp>.

doctor, an excellent man (i.e. sage and prudent), a man of great value, and a brave cavalier. In the modern *Treccani* dictionary of Italian, the first definition refers to someone who is ‘good, skilful, and capable in his profession or art’¹⁸; the other meanings from *Crusca* are considered obsolete. Ganassi’s *valente* master is therefore an excellent professional.

Achieving excellence as an objective was already prescribed in *Regola Rubertina* (chapter 15):

Note that here ends the first rule, which taught you both the name of the strings and their number as well as how to tune such an instrument solo and in consort; with the way of holding the viol and how to carry the body, to practice the hand [i.e. to develop finger and bow technique] and other necessary things to reach excellence in playing such an instrument solo and in consort.¹⁹

Likewise in chapter 20: ‘... following you will find four *ricercari* in several modes, which will be very appropriate for you to become excellent on this instrument’.²⁰ But in the dedication of *Letzione Seconda*, Ganassi puts it a little differently:

So having already finished my third effort [i.e. book] to teach what belongs to the perfect playing of the viol and the lute, and seeing it all rough and unornamented, I was thinking to whom I should send it, who with a liberal and joyful countenance would accept it as a duty.²¹

The adjective ‘perfect’ here is the clue to understand what lies behind Ganassi’s pedagogical ideas: the oratory of Cicero (1st century AD). For the Renaissance, the famous Roman orator was the ultimate authority, the great classical model to be imitated, sometimes almost blindly (and therefore, there were also many discussions about the exaggerated use of his work as the only possible source on literary emulation).²² So it is not surprising that Ganassi’s treatises have a strong Ciceronian accent in many respects, which we have only enough space to discuss briefly here.²³ To start with, we need to pay attention to Cicero’s short dialogue called *Orator*, the objective of which is to describe what a perfect orator would be like.²⁴ Transposing a perfect model based on this dialogue to other activities or professions was a favourite

¹⁸‘Bravo, esperto, abile, capace nella sua professione, arte, disciplina, o in qualche determinata attività.’ *Treccani*, s.v. ‘Valente.’

¹⁹‘Nota che qui finisce la prima regola laquale t’ha insignato: si lo nome delle corde & quantita come ancora l’acordar il ditto istromento solo, & accompagnato con il modo de tenir la viola, & portamento della persona, & praticar la mano, & altre cose necessarie per pervenir alla eccellentia in sonar ditto istromento solo, & accompagnato.’

²⁰‘si che seguita che tu troverai quattro ricercari di modi variati, che ti sera molto in proposito al pervenir eccellente in questo istromento’.

²¹‘La onde havendo io gia finita la mia terza fatica dell’insegnare quello che al perfettamente sonare di Viuola & di Liuto s’apperteneva, & vedendola tutta rozza & disornata, pensavo a cui ne la dovesse inviare che con liberale & lieto volto la fusse per dover accettare.’

²²See for example, Erasmus of Rotterdam, *Ciceronianus* (1528) and discussions of it; also Tettamanti, ‘Talking Cards’, 120.

²³It will be discussed at length in my forthcoming doctoral thesis.

²⁴See Cicero, *Brutus; Orator*, trans. G. L. Hendrickson and H. M. Hubbell, rev. ed. (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2014).

game of Renaissance literati, a commonplace in this culture. Several books that are still famous resulted from this practice: for example, *The Book of the Courtier* (1528) by Baldassare Castiglione and Machiavelli's *The Prince* (1532). In music, we can recall the famous quotation from Gioseffo Zarlino's *Istitutione Harmoniche* (1558) about the perfect musician being capable of mastering both theory and practice in his art:

The musician is the one who is expert [*perito*] in music and has the faculty of judging, not through the sound, but through the reason which is contained in this science. If he can also do the things that belong to practice, he would make his science more perfect: and then he can be called a perfect musician.²⁵

Following his contemporaries and anticipating Zarlino, Ganassi presents here his own model of the perfect player of the viol and the lute, whom he calls 'the *valente* master of this and those instruments'.²⁶

In the beginning of *Orator*, Cicero points out that he is not describing a real person, past or present, but rather, an idea of perfection that resides in the mind of the craftsman.²⁷ He gives the example of Phidias, the most famous of Greek sculptors, who, when making statues of Zeus [Jupiter] and Athena [Minerva], had his hand guided by a certain supreme idea of beauty in his mind, which he imprinted on the stone – not the copy of a living model before his eyes but an image superior to reality, created by reason, an image capable of representing what these gods would have been like if they had suddenly materialized in front of our eyes. In another dialogue, *De inventione*, Cicero compares the way he created his books on oratory to the pictorial art of Zeuxis, who, when painting the beautiful Helen of Troy, based her on the five most beautiful virgins of Cortona, taking from each one what was best, because in nature nothing is perfect in all parts.²⁸ He also remarks that, in other subjects, if people choose to take the best contributions of many authors instead of devoting themselves exclusively to one, they would avoid falling into arrogance.²⁹

Ganassi—a product of this very Cicero-oriented culture, which includes exercising *humilitas* as a moral virtue—is not merely being humble when he states in chapter 1 of *Regola Rubertina*, after giving instructions on how to hold the instrument: 'and certainly I myself do not have the most pleasant and beautiful hold of such an instrument as is the way I have described to you'.³⁰ He is actually describing not himself, or any other specific musician, but an idea of perfection that was created in his mind, from his experience and observation of the best practices of his peers. In the same way, when Ganassi mentions the names of some famous players, he does not say that they are perfect in everything. Of the six instrumentalists mentioned in *Letzione Seconda*, two of them, Giuliano Tiburtino and Lodovico Lasagnino, are

²⁵'Musico esser colui, che nella Musica è perito, & hà facultà di giudicare, non per il suono: ma per ragione quello, che in tale scienza si contiene. Il quale se alle cose appartenenti alla pratica darà opera, farà la sua scienza più perfetta: & Musico perfetto si potrà chiamare.' Parte prima, cap. 11. My translation. The passage is longer than this and well worth reading in full.

²⁶'valente di tal strumento e strumenti'. Ganassi, *Letzione Seconda*, title.

²⁷Cicero, *Orator*, book I, [7–9].

²⁸Cicero, *De inventione*, book II, [1–5]; *De inventione; De optimo genere oratorum; Topica*, trans. H. M. Hubbell (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1949), 168–69.

²⁹Cicero, *De inventione*, book II, [4].

³⁰'e per certo non ho appreso di me il piu grato e bello tenir ditto stromento quanto e con il modo che v'ho descritto'.

used to embody the art of *cantare alla viola*; whereas the other four, the viol players Alfonso da Ferrara and Giovanni Battista Ciciliano, and the lutenists Francesco da Milano and Rubertino Mantovano, are exalted as experts in the art of playing diminutions using notes that go beyond the frets of the instrument.³¹ It is also worth mentioning the remarkable citation in *Regola Rubertina* of Emperor Charles V's Court composer Nicolas Gombert (c. 1495–c. 1560) – for Ganassi, the ‘true chapel master’³²—and his method of accommodating the music to the range of the available singers. Ganassi, then, created his works, like Cicero and Zeuxis, by collecting the best actions and ideas from the best masters around.

Erwin Panofsky explains that this Ciceronian view of the arts uses the Platonic concept of ideas to rescue the arts from the Platonic concept of art itself, since for Plato art had no value, being considered a mere copy of the visible world, imperfect and inferior to nature.³³ Cicero, then, makes use of the Platonic idea to aim for an art based on the craftsman's reason, superior to nature and capable of correcting its own imperfections. Ganassi shows himself aligned with this Ciceronian vision when he repeats, in no fewer than five places in his works, the motto *Dove manca la natura, che l'arte sia maestra* (Where nature fails, may art be master).³⁴

In summarizing what the perfect orator should be like, in his other dialogues Cicero recalls Cato the Elder's maxim *Orator est vir bonus dicendi peritus* (The orator is a good man, expert in the art of speaking).³⁵ We need to take into account that rhetoric had been completely discredited by Plato in his *Gorgias* for having served unscrupulous purposes, later being rescued by Aristotle, who linked it to commitment to the truth; when the art arrived in Ancient Rome, it was already intrinsically bound to ethics.³⁶ A little later than Cicero, in the preface to his *Institutio oratoria* (c. AD 95), Quintilian confirms: ‘We establish that only the good man can be the perfect orator; therefore, we require of him not only the exceptional ability to speak, but all the virtues of the spirit.’³⁷ He follows up by saying that orators are more suitable than philosophers to administer public and private affairs. Even though we rely on philosophers' books to learn about virtues (e.g. justice, courage and temperance), this subject belongs completely to the art of oratory. According to him, the virtues were enumerated by Cicero and connected by nature and practice in such a manner that orators could also be considered wise.³⁸

In reading Ganassi's three works, we may observe there is a change in the writing style of *Regola Rubertina* and *Letzione Seconda* in relation to *Fontegara*: what seems to be a parallel discourse of a moral religious nature crops up and runs through almost every chapter. This peculiarity even made the translator of these treatises into French hypothesize that Ganassi was

³¹ Chaps. 16 and 20.

³² ‘si come osserva il vero maestro di capella detto GOMBERTO’. *Regola Rubertina*, chap. 11.

³³ Erwin Panofsky, *Idea: A Concept in Art Theory*, trans. Joseph J. S. Peake (Columbia, SC: University of South Carolina Press, 1968), 13.

³⁴ *Fontegara*, chaps. 4 and 25; *Regola Rubertina*, chaps. 5 and 7; *Letzione Seconda*, chap. 4.

³⁵ Cicero, *Ad quintum*, book XII, 1, [1]; *De oratore*, book II, [85].

³⁶ See more in Cicero, *De inventione*, book I, [1–4].

³⁷ ‘Oratorem autem instituimus illum perfectum, qui esse nisi vir bonus non potest; ideoque non dicendi modo eximiam in eo facultatem sed omnes animi virtutes exigimus.’ Quintilian, *Institutio oratoria*, book 1, preface, [9]. My translation based on Quintiliano, *Instituição oratória*, tomo I, trans. Bruno Fregni Bassetto (Campinas, SP, Brazil, 2015), which has a closer relationship to the original text than the standard English translations do.

³⁸ Quintilian, *Institutio oratoria*, book 1, preface, [10–13].

a cleric,³⁹ which was far from reality: he had a public job as a musician and was even married twice. The change of tone can also be credited to a measure of security against the increase in censorship caused by the Counter-Reformation in texts published in the 1540s, especially Venetian ones.⁴⁰ But when we look at these books through the lens of the ‘perfect orator’, we understand that this moral discourse is not in fact parallel but an intrinsic part of the whole, a part that cannot be ignored. If to be perfect the orator needs to be a good man (*vir bonus*), then the perfect viol player, the *valente* master, also needs to be a good man, so the moral discourse becomes necessary. If you want to achieve excellence, based on this model of perfection, you must learn not only what belongs to music and to instrumental technique, but also the virtues of ethics. This morality that Ganassi teaches is based on Aristotelian ethics, on Christian ethics from the medieval tradition, and above all on Ciceronian ethics.

The clue for this last is in a passage of *Regola Rubertina*’s dedication letter that has been misinterpreted by scholars. Ganassi starts it by quoting Socrates in capital letters and continues by associating him with the immortality of the soul and the music of the spheres:

The most celebrated and revered proverb that exists in antiquity, almost given by the mouth of God, the illustrious Lord, is this: KNOW THYSELF; that is, the substance of thy soul. And because the soul is harmony, as the best philosophers like, it is the same to say ‘Know thyself’ as ‘Know harmony’, which, as a necessary thing, was even instituted by theologians in their temples and by philosophers in their Re.Pu., where they had as their first precept and main instruction that harmony is necessary and appropriate for all rational and proportionate men almost by natural instinct. This instinct was the reason why, in my early years, led by the beauty of harmony, I did nothing else than think about it, speak about it and practice it. But because I could not, from the mediocrity of my ingenuity and the paucity of my fortune, penetrate the inner beauty of that harmony which is in our soul [*musica humana*] and in all high and eternal things [*musica mundana*], I have spent time sketching this [other] harmony, image of that, which is more common to our senses and is in the proportion of voices and instruments [*musica instrumentalis*].⁴¹

³⁹‘We put forward the hypothesis that he was a cleric.... Ganassi peppers his remarks with biblical quotations and references, and we see him constantly attached to the love of his neighbour, indications, for us, of a clerical position.’ My translation. Silvestro Ganassi, *Œuvres complètes*, II, ed. Christine Vossart; intro, trans. & notes by Jean-Philippe Navarre (Sprimont, Belgium: Mardaga, 2004), Introduction, 11.

⁴⁰See, for example, Christopher Cairns, *Pietro Aretino and the Republic of Venice: Research on Aretino and his Circle in Venice 1527–1556* (Florence: Olschki, 1985), 110–12; Titan, ‘Origins of Instrumental Diminution’, 176.

⁴¹‘Il piu celebrato & riverito proverbio, che habbia lantighita, & quasi dato dalla bocca di Dio illustre signor è questo CONOSCI TE MEDESIMO cioe la sostanza dell’anima tua: e perche l’anima è armonia, come piacque a miglior filosofi, tanto e a dire conosci te medesimo, quanto conosci l’armonia, la quale come cosa necessaria fu etiamdio instituita da teologi ne lor tempj, e da filosofi nelle lor Re.Pu. la dove essendo primo precetto e principale institution l’armonia è necessaria e debita ad ogni huomo ragionevole e proportionato quasi per instinto naturale: il quale instinto è stata cagione, che io da miei primi anni menato dalla vaghezza de l’armonia, non ho mai fatto altro, che pensar dessa, parlar dessa, & essercitarmi in essa: ma perche non ho potuto per la mediocrita del mio ingegno, e per la bassezza de la mia fortuna, penetrar alla bellezza interiore di quella armonia, che sta nell’anima nostra, & in tutte le cose alte & eterne, sono andato ad ombrando questa armonia, ch’è piu commune al senso nostro, & è imagine di quella, che sta nella proportion delle voci & delli istrumenti....’

Note he states that harmony was instituted as a necessary thing by philosophers in their *Res Publica* [*Re.Pu.*]. Perhaps because these two words were abbreviated, and therefore hard to understand, the first English translator, Richard Bodig, simply cut them out of the text.⁴² Dina Titan, focusing on Plato's *Republic*, cites the passage as part of her argument that Ganassi's *Regola Rubertina* has 'Neoplatonic overtones'.⁴³ But the reference alludes to philosophers and the possessive pronoun for their works is in the plural. Jean-Philippe Navarre, the French translator, was more accurate in affirming that it refers to Plato and Aristotle's books about the organization of the city (i.e. Plato's *Republic* and Aristotle's *Politics*),⁴⁴ and indeed, in the 1540s,⁴⁵ a translation of Aristotle's *Politics* made by Antonio Brucioli (also from the Rucellai circle in Florence) was published in Venice and dedicated to Ruberto Strozzi's brother Piero, under the title *Gli otto libri della Repubblica che chiamono Politica di Aristotile*. Brucioli himself in his *Dialogi* (Venice, 1526, 2 1537) wrote a dialogue about the Republic that includes some Aristotelian ideas. It is important to note that these Florentine exiles, Ganassi's audience, were republicans as a way of opposing the Medici control of power.

A third fundamental *Republic* not yet mentioned by Ganassi scholars is that of Cicero, known in the Middle Ages and Renaissance only from its epilogue, which they called *The Dream of Scipio*, preserved thanks to Macrobius's commentary in the fourth century. *The Dream* was in fact the only extract from the *Republic* known until the nineteenth century. It was translated into Italian, also by Brucioli, before 1539.⁴⁶ The work is a short moral text, and the first source to link a reward after death to those who lived a virtuous life on earth; this content fits perfectly with the subject mentioned by Ganassi in his dedication letter, even including a passage about the music of the spheres. The connection of Socrates with the immortality of the soul (the main theme of *The Dream*) is made in two other texts from Cicero: *De senectute* [On Old Age] and *De amicitia* [On Friendship]. The latter two texts are included in a collection of Cicero's works that was printed in Venice no fewer than eight times between 1523 and 1564, *The Dream* being added to it in 1539.⁴⁷ The collection also included *De officiis* [On Duties] and *Paradoxa stoicorum* [Stoic Paradoxes]. The two last editions, corrected by Lodovico Dolce, appeared under the more explicit title *Opere morali di Cicerone* [Moral works of Cicero]. Ganassi uses the content of all five of these works in his moral sermons in both *Regola Rubertina* and *Letzione Seconda*.⁴⁸

⁴²Richard D. Bodig, 'Ganassi's *Regola rubertina*', *Journal of the Viola da Gamba Society of America*, 18 (1981), 14. It has since been published in book form: *Regola Rubertina and Letzione seconda: Venice 1542-1543*, trans. Richard Bodig (Australia: Saraband Music, 2002).

⁴³Titan, 'Origins of Instrumental Diminution', 174-77.

⁴⁴'L'auteur vise d'abord Platon, puis sans doute Aristote, dans leurs ouvrages sur l'organisation de la Cité.' Ganassi, *Ceuvres complètes*, II, trans. Navarre, 19, n. 4.

⁴⁵The title page of the book gives the publication date as 1547, but the colophon at the end says 1542. It is possible that the V of the VII was omitted in error from the colophon. In any case, the book doubtless circulated in manuscript before it was published.

⁴⁶*Il Sogno di Scipione di Marco Tullio Cicerone, cavato del libro della Repubblica*. The first edition bears no date, but the second was published in 1539. See *Dizionario Biografico degli Italiani*, XIV (1972), s.v. 'Brucioli, Antonio', by Robert N. Lear.

⁴⁷*L'Opere di M. T. Cicerone* (Venice, 1523); *Di Marco Tullio Cicerone degl'Ufficij* (1528, 1536); *Opere di M. T. Cicerone* (1539); *Le Opere di M. T. Cicerone* (1540); *Opere di M. T. Cicerone* (1544); *Opere morali di M. T. Cicerone* (1563); *Opere morali* (1564).

⁴⁸For details, see my forthcoming thesis.

According to David Lines, no serious scholar considers the Renaissance as the Age of Plato any longer.⁴⁹ Rather, there was an increase of interest in Aristotle's works, a mixing of the schools of thought of Plato, Aristotle and Stoicism, and also an attempt to reconcile them, as had been done in ancient Rome. In my understanding, the importance of Cicero to Renaissance culture was responsible for this tendency. Although Ganassi rarely cites names, in his treatises we find abundant references to both Aristotle and Cicero; all the Stoicism and Platonism in his thought comes from either Cicero or the church tradition.

Explaining ethics – 1. The good man

The concept of a good man, *vir bonus*, follows in its essence the Greek concept of *kalokagathia*, formed by combining the terms *kalós* and *agathós*, the beautiful and the good, where the beautiful is everything that is well proportioned and consistent with nature, and the good everything that performs its function fully. Such characteristics grant the citizen of the *polis* a nobility that depends more on character and practice than on birth, through an excellence that is not given but achieved and constructed.⁵⁰ In Aristotle's *Nicomachean Ethics*, good is related to how you perform your activities:

If then the function of man is the active exercise of the soul's faculties in conformity with rational principle, or at all events not in dissociation from rational principle, and if we acknowledge the function of an individual and of a good individual of the same class (for instance, a harper and a good harper, and so generally with all classes) to be generically the same, the qualification of the latter's superiority in excellence being added to the function in his case (I mean that if the function of a harper is to play the harp, that of a good harper is to play the harp well): if this is so, and if we declare that the function of man is a certain form of life, and define that form of life as the exercise of the soul's faculties and activities in association with rational principle, and say that the function of a good man is to perform these activities well and rightly, and if a function is well performed when it is performed in accordance with its own proper excellence – from these premises it follows that the Good of man is the active exercise of his soul's faculties in conformity with excellence or virtue, or if there be several human excellences or virtues, in conformity with the best and most perfect among them.⁵¹

Ganassi, in accordance with this idea, has the following prologue in *Regola Rubertina*:

Worthy reader, you must know that in all faculties it is proper to have beauty and goodness. The beauty in the player is recognized in holding his instrument with grace and in [having] the posture of the hands and the movement of the

⁴⁹David Lines, introduction to Lines and Sabrina Ebbersmeyer, ed., *Rethinking Virtue, Reforming Society: New Directions in Renaissance Ethics, c.1350–c.1650* (Turnhout: Brepols, 2013), 3–4.

⁵⁰See Emilio Lledó Íñigo, introduction to Aristotle, *Ética nicomáquea – Ética eudemia* (Madrid: Editorial Gredos, 1977), 27.

⁵¹Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, book I, 7, 1098a [5–15], trans. H. Rackham, 2nd ed. (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1934), 33.

body in such a balanced way that it induces the listeners to stay in silence, so that they come to taste goodness, which is food for the ear, just as beauty feeds the sight. And if beauty consists in holding the instrument and [playing] with proportionate movements, also goodness will be recognized in knowing how to form the species (or consonances) in their places (or compositions), and making diminutions (or *passaggi*) in such a way that it does not offend the art [with such things] as vices, errors in counterpoint, and forbidden compositional devices, as you will be taught about all these in the following.⁵²

In other words, goodness here has nothing to do with generosity but with playing correctly, to perform your function as a musician well.

The first two chapters of *Regola Rubertina* deal with beauty. First, ‘How to hold the viol’,⁵³ where harmony of posture is valued, and strange and grotesque positions are avoided (he calls them *moresca* movements). Second, ‘About the body’s movement’,⁵⁴ which seeks a balance between having to move ‘so as not to appear to be made of stone’⁵⁵ and affectation. He gives as another reason for moving the body that ‘music well-composed according to the words’ requires it.⁵⁶ The objective is to imitate the nature of words, not only with the movements of the body but also the articulation of the bow. We should remember that the target audience of the treatises were avid consumers of the madrigal and participated in a *ridotto* under the musical direction of Willaert, recognized and celebrated for knowing better than anyone how to compose according to the words. The model to follow is the orator. Ganassi says: ‘and this conversation of mine is as relevant and necessary as are for the orator audacity, exclamation [two rhetorical devices], gestures, movements, and sometimes imitating laughing and crying in accordance with the subject and other suitable things. And if you put your reason in order [i.e. think straight], you will not find that the orator laughs at words of crying...’⁵⁷

The remaining content of *Regola Rubertina* deals with goodness, that is, how to tune and play well and correctly, both alone and in consort. In *Letzione Seconda*, Ganassi gives us a clear definition of the four elements that constitute goodness, through which we can practice acting as a *valente* master:

First you must know this: that for the sufficient [i.e. competent] master of such an instrument, his sufficiency is caused by four actions that he takes, of which

⁵²‘Degno lettor hai da saper come in ogni faculta se gli conviene bellezza e bonta, la bellezza nel sonator si conosce nel tenir il suo stromento con gratia & portamento della mano & motto di persona di tal equalita che induca gli audienti a prestarli silentio, accio venghino a gustar la bonta, la qual e cibo dellaudito, si come la bellezza ciba il vedere, e si la bellezza consiste nel tenir lo stromento e con movimenti proportionati, la bonta sera ancora essa conosciuta per lo saper formar le specie over consonantie ne gli suoi termini over componimenti & con il diminuire over passazi de maniera tale che non habbia di offendere l’arte. Come vitii, & errori nel contra ponto, & composition prohibiti come seguendo del tutto serai ammaestrato.’

⁵³‘Modo de tenir la viola.’

⁵⁴‘Del movimento de la persona.’

⁵⁵‘per non parer essere di pietra’.

⁵⁶‘per causa de la musica ben composta su le parole’.

⁵⁷‘e questo mio raggionamento è in tanto proposito & necessario, quanto è ne l’oratore audatia esclamation gesti movimenti, & alle volte imitar il ridere, & il pianger per la conformita de la materia, & altre cose conveniente: e se tu poni la raggione in regola non trovarai che l’oratore rida per le parole del pianto...’

four, two are masters and two are disciples. The main and master is to know from music its consonances (or species); the second part, as disciple, is to play the thing correctly – I mean, as it is composed. The third part, as master, is to know the rules of counterpoint; and the fourth part, as disciple of this counterpoint, is to make diminutions correctly, as is suitable in ornamenting compositions.⁵⁸

Next he says that the two master parts can be learned through ‘rules’, that is, from books. This foreshadows Zarlino’s ‘perfect musician’, whose perfection lies at the junction of theoretical and practical knowledge, or in Ciceronian terms, in a practice based on reason.

Returning to the perfect viol player, we have seen that he has to be good, and this includes not only fulfilling his function, his purpose, in a correct and balanced way (i.e. with beauty), but also being a good human being through the practice of virtues (or excellences).⁵⁹ For Aristotle, virtues are dispositions of the soul that are worthy of praise. He divides them into two categories: intellectual and moral. The intellectual virtues are wisdom, understanding and prudence (practical wisdom); they are produced and expanded by instruction and therefore require time and experience. The moral virtues (or virtues of character) are the product of habit and are related not to knowledge itself, but to moderation and sobriety.⁶⁰

2. Moral virtues

Moral virtues are a mean between two vices, one caused by exaggeration and the other by lack. They include courage, the mean between cowardice and temerity; generosity, the mean between pettiness and prodigality; and magnanimity, the mean between vanity and smallness of soul, etc. The theme of temperance, the golden mean, between two extremes had been a favourite of Ganassi’s since *Fontegara*: he refers to it numerous times,⁶¹ as well as to Aristotelian mottos such as ‘between two evils, choose the lesser’.⁶²

⁵⁸‘Per prima tu hai di saper questo ch’l sufficiente maestro di tal’istromento la sua sufficientia e causada da quattro parte di adottamento in lui & di queste quattro parte due son le maestre & due discipuli. La principal & maestra sie il saper della musica le sue consonantie over specie, & la seconda parte come discipola e il sonar la cosa positiva e dico come la e sta composta & la terza parte come maestra sie il saper le regole dil contraponto & la quarta parte come discipola di esso contraponto sie il diminuir la cosa positiva come conviensi ne l’ornamento alle composition.’ Chap. 17.

⁵⁹The Greek term *areté* was translated by Latin writers as *virtus*. Nowadays scholars prefer to use the English word *excellence* rather than *virtue*. See J. O. Urmson, *The Greek Philosophical Vocabulary* (London: Duckworth, 1990), 30–31.

⁶⁰Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, book I, 13, 1103a1 [5–10] and book II, 1, 1103a1 [15–20].

⁶¹See, e.g., *Fontegara*, chaps. 2, 5 and 24; *Regola Rubertina*, chaps. 2, 4, 9 and 11; and *Letzione Seconda*, chaps. 1–3 and 8; see also Lasocki and Ehrlich, *The Recorder*, 62–72; Silva, ‘Gammaut’.

⁶²‘di duoi mali elegersi il minore’; *Regola Rubertina*, chap. 11. ‘ogni volta che havesti a elegere de dui mali uno de quelli sempre tu debbi a elegere il manco’; *Letzione Seconda*, chap. 8.

Table 1: The Seven Deadly Sins and Remedial Virtues

Seven Deadly Sins	Seven Remedial Virtues
Lust	Chastity
Envy	Charity/Love
Gluttony	Abstinence
Sloth	Diligence
Wrath	Patience
Greed	Benevolence
Pride	Humility

Table 2: Moral Virtues cited by Ganassi

Cardinal Virtues	Virtues as Found in Ganassi
Prudence	The aware master (LS)
Fortitude	Patience (RR/LS) Frequency [constancy] (RR/LS) Diligence (RR)
Temperance	Sobriety (RR) Abstinence (RR/LS)
Justice	Charity (RR/LS) Liberality (LS) Humility (RR/LS)
Remedial Virtues	Charity (RR/LS) Abstinence (RR/LS) Patience (RR/LS) Humility (RR/LS) Diligence (RR)
Theological Virtues	Faith (RR) Hope (RR) Charity (RR)

In addition to the Aristotelian concept, the medieval Christian tradition revived, through the work of Cicero (*De inventione*), Macrobio (*Commentarii in somnium Scipionis*) and others, the four virtues of the perfect *polis* of Plato's *Republic*—wise, courageous, temperate and just—adding to them the many other virtues as subcategories following a system that originated with Cicero and Macrobio. Plato's virtues were later known as the four cardinal virtues: prudence, fortitude, temperance and justice. To the cardinal virtues the church added three theological ones, extracted from the famous letter of Saint Paul to the Corinthians (1:13): faith, hope and charity, to form the seven Christian virtues. In their writings, theologians focused on virtues. In contrast, the pastoral literature of confession manuals, which had the

objective of converting people, emphasized their opposite, the seven capital vices (deadly sins), and created the seven remedial virtues to counteract them.⁶³

Table 2 shows the moral virtues cited by Ganassi in *Regola Rubertina* (RR) and *Letzione Seconda* (LS), organized by me as subcategories of the four cardinal virtues as well as part of the remedial and theological virtues.

The epilogues of *Regola Rubertina* and *Letzione Seconda* give us a good taste of the fatherly way, as he puts it, in which Ganassi recommends the virtues to his readers:

Now you listen to me.

If you want to acquire many virtues in a short time, learn to learn; and wanting to know how to learn, it is necessary to use diligence along with its many necessary parts, especially the following three, that is: frequency, patience and abstinence – frequency for the time, patience for the tiredness, and abstinence for the inclination [i.e. the temptation to fall into vices].⁶⁴

... you will deliberate [i.e. choose] to want to use patience with frequency and abstain from all impediments that would be contrary to your study, as was also given as a sentence at the end of *Rubertina*. And about this reminder of exhortation I will say no other word, except that I will humble myself to your grace, Wise Reader, [hoping] that you want to accept my effort, such as it is, as the father's advice given to his son, which I will certainly say because of the love and good will I have for you, most humanistic Reader....⁶⁵

According to Cicero, diligence is divided into six parts: care, attention, reflection, awareness, constancy and effort.⁶⁶ Ganassi exhorts that, in order to be excellent, you need to use all the parts of diligence, but especially constancy (frequency, to keep going day after day), patience (to work through the tiredness), and abstinence (from anything that can distract you from your work).

⁶³See István Bejczy, *The Cardinal Virtues in the Middle Ages: A Study in Moral Thought from the Fourth to the Fourteenth Century* (Leiden; Boston: Brill, 2011), 233–39.

⁶⁴'Hora ascoltami. Se vuoi acquistiar molte virtu in breve tempo, impara ad imparare, & volendo saper imparare è dibisogno usar la diligentia accompagnata tra le molte parti necessarie alla materia principalmente da queste tre, che è la frequentation, la patientia, & l'astinentia, la frequentation per il tempo, la patientia per la fatica, l'astinentia per la inclination.' See also *Regola Rubertina*, letter to readers and chap. 7, as wonderful examples of how Ganassi constructs a great mixture of moral virtues, theological virtues, vices, capital sins and remedial virtues as well as advice from *On Duties*, *On Old Age*, and *Stoic Paradoxes* (especially no. 6: only the wise man is rich).

⁶⁵'... tu te deliberarai a voler usar la patientia con il frequentar & astenirti da tutti l'impedimenti che fusse contrarii al studio tuo, come e ancora ditto in sententia in fin della Rubertina, & di questo aricordo de esortation non ne faro altro moto salvo che me humiliaro alla tua gratia Sapiente Lettor che tal e qual mia fatica tu la vogli accettar come il consiglio del padre dato al figliolo che certamente diro quanto all'amor & bon voler mio verso dite humanissimo Lettor....'

⁶⁶Cicero, *De oratore*, book II, [150].

3. Intellectual virtues and the aware master (the prudent)

Despite being part of the cardinal virtues, prudence is actually one of the Aristotelian intellectual virtues, which do not refer to character but represent parts of the rational side of reason (the impulses being the irrational side). This rational side can be developed through instruction and is divided into five parts: science, art, prudence, intellect and wisdom. 'Science' refers to what we know and can be demonstrated; 'art' belongs to an action that produces something; 'prudence' is the ability to deliberate about what is good or bad; 'intellect' is the capacity through which we know the truth; and 'wisdom' arises from the conjunction of intellect with science, that is, intelligence and knowledge.⁶⁷

Of these virtues, prudence is of particular interest for our purposes. Aristotle states that the prudent person is 'capable of deliberating correctly about what is good and convenient for himself, not in a partial sense, for example, for health, for strength, but for living well in general.... it is a true and practical way of being rational about what is good and bad for man.'⁶⁸ Prudence is generally linked to moderation, since a man corrupted by pleasure or pain loses the ability to deliberate properly, because vices destroy the principle of all good action. It is therefore practical wisdom. Later, Aristotle mentions a second type of prudence, political, where the prudent person is capable of deliberating wisely what is good for both self and others; normally these people are politicians or administrators.⁶⁹ In Machiavelli's *The Prince*, prudence is the adjective par excellence of his model of perfection. For example: 'a prudent man should always enter upon the paths beaten by great men, and imitate those who have been most excellent'.⁷⁰ 'It is necessary for him [the prince] to be so prudent as to know how to avoid the infamy of those vices that would take his state from him'.⁷¹ Earlier we mentioned the entry for *valente* in the first edition of the *Crusca* dictionary. In its second example, we find the following quotation from Boccaccio: '... and like a worthy gentleman [*valente huomo*] be satisfied to have taken thy revenge', with an addition by the authors of the dictionary between brackets, 'that is, sage and prudent'.⁷² Here we see how they give the essence of an excellent man in these two intellectual virtues, one representing theoretical wisdom and the other practical.

Ganassi, in his model of a perfect player, does not use 'prudent' but another term that means the same thing: 'the aware master'.⁷³ The adjective he employs is *avertido*, derived from the verb *avertire*, which means to become conscious of something, to realize something, and also in literature, to pay attention to something.⁷⁴ As an adjective it means aware (the quality of the master); and as a noun, *avertentia*, it means the cautions that the master needs to know in order to be aware. Then the aware master, like the prudent man, is the one who deliberates well about what is good and bad in his playing. In order to do this deliberation, he needs to know his art and all its tools very well, being sure to call on all the available ones, as we can

⁶⁷ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, book VI, 1–8, 1138b [20]–1142a [30].

⁶⁸ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, book VI, 5, 1140a [25] and 1140b.

⁶⁹ Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, book VI, 8, 1141b [25]–1142a [30].

⁷⁰ Niccolò Machiavelli, *The Prince*, trans. Harvey C. Mansfield, 2nd ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1998), 22.

⁷¹ *Ibid.*, 62.

⁷² 'Bocc. n. 77.37. E come a valente huomo, sieti assai l'esserti potuto venticare [cioè savio e prudente].' Boccaccio, *Decameron*, 8th day, novel 7, [80].

⁷³ 'maestro avertido'.

⁷⁴ *Treccani*, s.v. 'Avvertire'.

learn, for example, from the next quotation.⁷⁵ Here Ganassi is explaining the importance of not changing strings so much in fast passages. If you do so, you will lose agility, the main quality that makes you be recognized as a master and not a student.

Note that this caution [*avertentia*] among many is of great utility for being one of the legitimate ones that make you really have the action of the *valente* master, in the same way as the craftsman who, I tell you, makes the said instrument. Every time he does not have the awareness [*l'avertir*] to prepare his appropriate tool to make his thing, or work – a cornice, say – the action in shaping this said cornice will always be equal to the preparation of the tool or chisel. This example will be more intelligible through another: that is, the matter will always accept the print given by the form. And we could also say, in another kind of example, that the perception a man has of an object [is] in conformity with the impression that it makes on him.⁷⁶ Therefore, if the tool or chisel has been formed with the reason appropriate for the work, the work will also always be made with reason; but if the said chisel were not used with awareness [*avertido*] in its purpose, because of its action the work would also remain lacking in its appropriate action....⁷⁷

After many examples he finally reveals in chapter 17 that all the elements of awareness in playing correspond to the ‘secrets’ of acting as a *valente* master that he had promised on the title page.

Now, having finished the debt of [teaching you] the manner of playing two parts and singing the third, there will follow the rest of the promise: that is [to show you] some solo ricercari. But [first] I will talk about some cautions [*avertentie*], I mean secrets, very useful in achieving the action of the true connoisseur in this practice.... As in *Fontegara* you have both the theory and practice of making diminutions, but concerning the practice of the instrument [viol or lute] in playing diminutions is not in any rule [i.e. book].... therefore, about those cautions

⁷⁵ See also chap. 10 about using all the necessary things for the work (*le cose bisognose nella opera*).

⁷⁶ Literally: ‘the impression of the man [is] in conformity with the case caused on him’. Ganassi seems to be using the doctrine of Saint Thomas Aquinas called *species impressa*. When someone is confronted with an object, the object first makes an impression on the mind, then the cognitive processes of the mind come to bear on the impression [*species expressa*]. The mind creates a concept of the object that is not the object *per se* but intrinsically connected to it. See *Catholic Encyclopedia*, s.v. ‘Species.’

⁷⁷ ‘Nota che tal avertentia tra le molte questa e id [sic] grande utilita per essere de le legittime che fa raf [sic] l’effetto in fatto da valente maestro si come ancora l’artifice che facia diro il ditto Stromento ogni volta chel non havesse l’avertir in prepararsi col ferro suo appropriado in tirar la cosa over opera sua diro una cornice sempre l’effetto suo in terminar ditta cornice sera tal e qual ne la prontation che sera nel ditto ferro over misterio come ancora tal essemplio si fa piu intelligibile per questo altro essemplio, che e che sempre la materia acetera lo impronto che li dara la forma & el si potria dir ancora in questo altro modo di essemplio che e questo la impression de l’omo conforme al caso per esso causada pero siando il ferro over misterio formato con rason conveniente a l’opera sempre l’opera sera fatta con rason ancora & quando che il ditto misterio non fusse avertido nel suo proposito ancora per il suo effetto l’opera seguitaria essere mancatrice ne l’effetto suo a proposito....’ *Lettonne Seconda*, chap. 19. This is also a fine example of how Ganassi in his treatises uses Aristotelian thought, in this case about matter and form.

[*avertentie*] or, better said, secrets, now in this work of mine I will provide their rules....⁷⁸

Because Ganassi's books are pedagogical, he is not limited to describing what the perfect viol player should be like; instead, he is teaching how to become as close as possible to one. Ganassi's works have not yet been explored at length, because of the difficulty of comprehending his language, and we still lack good translations. For this reason, I now give some highlights of what he expects musically from the *valente* master, not only having skill but also being prepared and resourceful.

The dynamics of the bow should follow the affect of the music, with the orator as the model (RR ch2). Test out different timbres by using the bow closer to the fingerboard (a sad affect) or the bridge (a crude sound) (RR ch4). Not only begin phrases with down bows, but be prepared to use up bows (as in his style of diminutions, which may contain odd numbers of notes) (RR ch6). Learn to read music as well as tablature (RR ch12–14, 19).

Tune the lowest string of the bass as low as possible within the tension of the strings, and if necessary, the bridge of the viol can be moved to lower its pitch even more. He observes how the taste of his period is against singers singing in too high a register, and gives as a solution for this problem a system used by Gombert in his chapel (RR ch11). Those tips also work for dealing with times when you have to play with instruments that are badly designed and therefore slightly away from the pitch standards (see RR ch7 for a colourful description of his strong opinions about bad makers). Learn all the several tunings for the viol consort, made up of three sizes of viol: bass, tenor/alto and soprano (RR ch9–18).⁷⁹ Still about tuning, he explains how to use barre chords to transpose half a tone or a tone to play with instruments at other pitch standards (LS ch20).

Know how to mark the frets on the instrument yourself with a pair of compasses, regardless of what the maker has done (LS ch4). After that, adjust the frets by ear: 'And this way will make you do the action with all excellence, because the thing created by reason and practice will be more perfect than that produced only by practice or only by reason' (LS ch5).⁸⁰ In doing so, he created a personal temperament which differs from those of other musicians of the time.⁸¹

In choosing strings to buy, learn to recognize the good string (*giusta*), which creates a

⁷⁸'Hor espedito il debito dil modo de sonar due parte e cantar la terza si seguiterà il resto della promessa che e de alcuni ricercari a sola voce pero te rasonaro de alcune avertentie e dico secreti de molto proposito per il pervenir a l'effetto del vero sciente in tal prattica.... Come nella Fontegara havete ancora la theorica & prattica del diminuir, ma di quanto la prattica dell'Istromento in far le diminution non e regola niuna per tanto tale avertentie o voglia dir secreti al presente in questa mia opera ti sera regolado....' *Letzione Seconda*, chap. 17.

⁷⁹First *incordatura*: D–G–D; second: D–A–D; third: D–G–C, which can also be done a tone higher as E–A–D; fourth, using the first but playing everything a fourth higher on the fingerboard.

⁸⁰'& tal ordine ti fara far l'effetto in ogni eccellentia perche la cosa formata dalla rason & prattica sera piu perfetta che quella che fusse proceduta dalla sola prattica ancora dalla sola rason'.

⁸¹Adam Wead, 'Lute Tuning and Temperament in the Sixteenth and Seventeenth Centuries' (DMus document, Indiana University, 2014), 55–61, points out that on the lute Ganassi starts with the Pythagorean system of tuning and then adjusts it by ear to create a mixed system, half Pythagorean and half tempered, but in a unique temperament 'that combines different types of semitones from different temperaments', unlike the practice of other sixteenth-century musicians such as Hans Gerle and John Dowland.

single firm wave when you pluck it, the bad (*falsa*), which ‘trembles like a paralytic’,⁸² and the in-between (*media*), which makes more than one wave but still firm. In-between strings are important because it is difficult, expensive and an endless process to string a viol, and even worse a lute, only with good strings, which are rare in any case. This is a good example of his discourse on the temperance of two extremes (Aristotelian moral virtues) (LS ch1–3).

He compares articulation on the lute to the diction of speech. He criticizes what he calls the common way of playing, the well-established Renaissance technique of alternating thumb and index finger; rather, he insists on using four fingers (thumb down; index, middle and ring up), the little finger keeping its role of anchoring the hand. This idea anticipates by more than 50 years a development in lute technique considered to have started only at the end of the century.⁸³ In discussing the madrigal that he gives as an example in the treatise,⁸⁴ he advises to first practice it in the common way (thumb and index alternation), then in the way he notes in his tablature: this trains your brain to identify difference. (LS ch21)

He indicates three types of action for the right hand on the lute: *picigo* (plucking ‘consonances’, or chords), *squarzo* (strumming them with the thumb down) and playing single notes in succession (LS ch8). Later, he explains why he considers the common way an incautious (*non avvertido*) way of proceeding and affirms that the *valente* master must distribute the effort among the four fingers. The fingers are here for your convenience, like the necessary tools for creating a work, and whoever does not use everything available has a dubious intention (is foolish). (LS ch10) The different types of articulation are used not only for distributing the effort among the fingers but to provide some variation of affect. Many things are left to be practiced because people have no idea how much can be done on the instrument; if they did, they would practice even more. Investigate many things, so you can discover many secrets. (LS ch14)

For bowing on the viol, he gives some advice on how to play more than one note in the same bow, not legato, but marking each note with a little accent (LS ch15). He teaches the practice of *cantare alla viola*, an emulation of *cantare al liuto*, saying that on the viol it is possible to play two voices and sing the third. If you want to play one more voice, you can use a bigger bow. To help you hold the strings on the chords, he advises using a small piece of wood (LS ch16). To make diminutions in the aware manner, you must master all the fingerings and changes of position, of which he gives several examples of what is efficient or not (LS ch17); as already mentioned above, do not change strings all the time during fast passages; it is better to finish a cadential trill on the fifth fret instead of the open string (LS ch19); and learn how to make diminutions above the frets, like the great masters (LS ch20). The final goal is to play diminutions with ‘agility that is the cause of affect without affectation, which is proper of the master, not of the student’ (LS ch17 and 19).⁸⁵ In chapter 21, he gives two *ricercari* to prac-

⁸²‘ma sera tremante simile al paralitico’. *Lezione Seconda*, chap. 2.

⁸³In Richard Allison’s *The Psalms of David in Meter* (1599), the second and ring finger are given extraordinarily active roles; the middle finger is often used instead of the thumb on the treble strings, not necessarily only in diminutions, and the ring finger is used in a variety of contexts which, earlier in the century, invariably would have been notated for either thumb or for index finger.’ Paul Beier, ‘Right Hand Position in Renaissance Lute Technique’, *Journal of the Lute Society of America*, 12 (1979), 17.

⁸⁴Identified by Dina Titan as ‘Io penso’ by Ian Ghero.

⁸⁵‘far le diminution oltra le altre cose con la agelita laqual e quella che causa affetto non affettato come e da maestro e non da scolaro’. ‘con quella agelita che fusse intesa per il modo da maestro & non da scolaro’.

tice all these things related to diminutions. I would like to highlight the importance of solo *ricercari*, for Ganassi and the whole Italian sixteenth-century culture, as a fundamental tool for acquiring and developing technique – not only to play them from treatises but also learn to improvise them. He finishes the book by teaching how to play with three and four lower strings, a very useful thing because they last longer and are more available than the upper two strings, which are hard to find and break often (LS ch22–23).

Vir bonus, peritus in playing

We have learned the philosophical background of Ganassi's conception of what the goal of an instrumentalist should be. He expects not only great technical ability on the instrument, but an attitude to learning with focus, perseverance and moderation. He aims for an art created by reason and a knowledge acquired through the conjunction of theory with practice (which, with experience, will take you towards wisdom and prudence). It is necessary to be good in both senses of the word: being a good, honest person and performing your activity well. The secrets of the *valente* master can be summarized as mastering the art by: gaining awareness; having knowledge of the tools and using all the available ones; deliberating and choosing those tools with reason; playing with promptitude and agility in order to perform with 'affect without affectation, which is proper of the master'; and, above all, being open to investigate, experiment and learn new skills and different ways of doing, which will create a close and individual relationship with your instrument. In times like ours, where standardisation is prevalent, to see how in Renaissance culture there was space for individuality to shine is a good prompt for us to go deeper in finding our own freedom of expression.